

BIT RATE AND LOCAL QUALITY CONTROL USING A RATE/DISTORTION CRITERION FOR ON-BOARD SATELLITE IMAGES COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

The method we present is developed as part of an on-board satellite images compression with target ratios greater than 6. Such a compression is required because of the weight and memory constraints of on-board equipment and must be integrated in a bit rate control scheme. In order to guarantee a high local quality on some critical areas, we have developed an adapted encoder which integrates a local quality constraint within a bit rate control. This encoder, based on a progressive transmission of information by using an EZW algorithm, realizes coding and bit rate regulation in the same time. Actually, our encoder is a quite different from Shapiro's one due to the integration of Regions Of Interest (ROI) by setting up a classification map. Such a technique allows to limit artifacts on ROI without creating too much degradation on the rest of the image.

1 INTRODUCTION

Satellite images offer a large amount of information but the weight and memory constraints is a constant worry for on-board equipment. Therefore, the storage but also the transmission of those information require on-board compression. Various studies on this subject prove that image compression with variable bit rate is better than algorithms which present a constant one. The transmission channel between earth and SPOT satellites being a constant bit rate network (50M-bits/s), we find here a paradox and have to interface, through a bit rate control, the encoder output and the transmission channel. For the SPOT5 application, the French Spatial Agency (CNES) [2] has set up a bit rate control based on a Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) (this control loop has also been tested on a wavelet transform). Such a method allows to reach compression ratios around 3 but the research of higher ratios (≥ 6) constrains us to modify the usual technologies to guarantee an improved local image quality. Therefore, we propose to use a wavelet transform (9-7 tap filters) [3] and to set up a local bit rate control with both rate and quality constraints.

2 PRINCIPLES OF THE LOCAL REGULATION AND NEW DATA STRUCTURATION

The initial assumption of our study is that the whole image can not be processed globally but must be cut into groups of lines, called Control Image Structures (CIS). We treat them successively like in SPOT5 application [4]. Whereas we fix a global bit rate, $\mathcal{R}_{tot}$, for the CIS, we realize an implicit local regulation inside this CIS. Our method consists of a classification of the wavelet coefficients of the CIS and subsequently of a progressive transmission of information in order to reach a relevant rate for each class. Such a way of transmission requires an embedded bit-stream, which can be obtained with algorithms like EZW (Embedded Zerotree of Wavelet) [6] or SPIHT (Set Partitioning In Hierarchical Trees) [5]. These algorithms take into account the residual dependences between some coefficients from different sub-bands. Moreover, these coefficients are related to a same spatial location in the original image. So, it appears of great interest to establish a new data organization by making trees, or vectors, of wavelet coefficients (Fig 1). These vectors are defined in the same way as Shapiro's method in EZW algorithm.

Figure 1: New structuration of coefficients into vectors

3 CLASSIFICATION

Despite a research of quite high compression ratios, we need a great quality of reconstruction. Indeed, some areas of image can be considered as Regions Of Interest (ROI) in the case of Earth Observation (breakwaters, boats...) and, after decoding, the experts must be able to interpret the results. In order to limit the artifacts on these critical areas, a classification of the wavelet coefficients has been set up.

3.1 Features of ROI

First of all, we must describe the problems we can meet with an encoder based on a wavelet transform. Then, we take out the features of the areas concerned with these artifacts (they become our ROI), and give them a relevant label in order to minimize errors after coding. Actually there are two main problems in the images. First, some ringing effects can appear around the boundaries between uniform and high activity areas, typically breakwaters of harbor. Second, we can see smoothing effects especially on uniform regions as the sea for example. So, we have to put a specific label on the vectors which belong to such areas.

3.2 Steps of classification

The classification takes two automatic successive steps. First, an energy-based threshold allows to discriminate two temporary classes of vectors. The first class is defined as the group of vectors, written Edges vectors (E), whose energy is over a given threshold and the second as the remaining vectors of the CIS, written Uniform vectors (U). All the energies are only computed for the high frequency components and we can therefore speak about "high frequency energy", HF energy. The energy-based threshold, T_{e_j} , is adapted for each CIS j but it is not only based on the mean HF energy, E_{HF_j} , of the current CIS (1):

$$T_{e_j} = \sum_{k=1}^3 \frac{(E_{HF_{j-k}}/4)}{3} \quad (1)$$

$$E_{HF_j} = \sum_{\text{coeff} \in (CIS(j) - LL_{CIS(j)})} \frac{\text{coeff}^2}{N_j}$$

where N_j represents the number of coefficients in the j^{th} CIS without taking into account those which belong to the lowest frequency subband.

A second stage, an integration of the local context, is necessary to improve this classification and to find the ROI mentioned above: the number of neighbors which present a same label as the current vector is evaluated and thus the neighborhood type is determined. This method allows to establish an hierarchical classification by dividing each previous class into two new groups. Four cases occur but they can be classified into only three labels by regrouping the two classes where ringing effects appear (Fig 2).

Figure 2: Scheme of the whole classification process applied on a CIS

Since the study presented in this paper deals only with ringing effects, we can also regroup the classes 1 and 2 under a same label and then, work with a labels map which presents only two classes. In this case, vectors of class 0 can be considered as Vector Of Interest and we must take care of their coding. For the image "Genoa", we show the final obtained classification (Fig 3).

Figure 3: Original SPOT5 image "Genoa" (© CNES - 2000×800)(a) and the classification map (250×100) (b) used in order to avoid ringing effects. ROI are in white.

4 LOCAL BIT RATE CONTROL

Once classification is set up, we have to code these coefficients and control the bit rate at the encoder output. After we have fixed the global bit rate for the CIS at $\mathcal{R}_{tot}$, we distribute it among the different classes so as to privilege the ROI. Our method consists of a local bit rate control based on a progressive transmission of information using an EZW encoder. Actually there are some differences between Shapiro's algorithm and ours. In our work, one EZW encoder is not related to the whole image but to both a CIS and a class: we have two embedded bit-streams for a CIS. So, four parameters must be defined per CIS, two for each class. The first ones are the threshold value over which a coefficient is significant and the second ones are the bit rates for each class. The two target rates for a CIS j will be written as $\mathcal{R}_{j,roi}$ for

ROI and $\mathcal{R}_{j_{rest}}$ for the remaining vectors. Actually, a joint optimization of the two parameters of each class allows an adapted coding of the wavelet coefficients, such as:

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{R}_{j_{roi}} = \mathcal{N}_{j_{roi}} \times r_{j_{roi}} \\ \mathcal{R}_{j_{rest}} = \mathcal{N}_{j_{rest}} \times r_{j_{rest}} \end{cases} \quad \text{with} \quad \begin{cases} r_{j_{roi}} = \mathcal{K}_j \times r_{j_{rest}} \\ \mathcal{R}_{j_{roi}} + \mathcal{R}_{j_{rest}} = \mathcal{R}_{tot} \end{cases}$$

where $r_{j_{roi}}$ and $r_{j_{rest}}$ represent the bit rates per coefficient for each class of the CIS j and $\mathcal{N}_{j_{roi}}$ and $\mathcal{N}_{j_{rest}}$ the numbers of coefficients in each group. The $\mathcal{K}_j$ value is quite important because it is related to the notion of quality. In order to find an automatic value for this parameter, a rate-distortion optimization is computed by using the following modelization for the rate and the Weighted Mean Square Error, WMSE, of a CIS j :

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{R}_j = \sum_{i=0}^{Nb_class-1} \mathcal{N}_{j_i} \times (R_{j_i}^0 - \beta_{j_i} \log_2 Q_{j_i}) \\ \mathcal{D}_j = \sum_{i=0}^{Nb_class-1} \mathcal{N}_{j_i} \delta_i \frac{Q_{j_i}^2}{12} \end{cases}$$

where Q_{j_i} is the quantization step for the class i of the CIS j , $R_{j_i}^0$ and β_{j_i} some characteristics of the CIS j and δ_i , the weight applied to the MSE of the class i for the minimization. Indeed, $\mathcal{K}_j$ is such that it minimizes a linear weighted combination of the MSE of the two classes under a rate constraint. The parameters $R_{j_i}^0$ and β_{j_i} are estimated on line but δ_{roi} and δ_{rest} are fixed to 2/3 and 1/3 respectively. Then, an automatic value can be found for $\mathcal{K}_j$; it depends on different features of the CIS (2):

$$\mathcal{K}_j = \frac{\beta_{j_{roi}} \mathcal{R}_{tot} + \mathcal{N}_{j_{rest}} \Gamma_j}{\beta_{j_{rest}} \mathcal{R}_{tot} - \mathcal{N}_{j_{roi}} \Gamma_j} \quad \text{with} \quad \Gamma_j = \text{constant} \quad (2)$$

Such an expression allows to privilege the Regions of Interest without creating too much degradation on the rest of the image.

5 RESULTS

The shown results were established for the image "Genoa" (Fig 3a) which includes some interesting areas for our study. For example, the bottom of the image presents great visual artifacts for a SPOT5 bit rate control since the applied compression ratio (≥ 6) is too high. The local regulation loop we have implemented allows to encode such critical areas with a better reconstruction quality.

First, we focus on the advantages of an implicit regulation towards a SPOT5 bit rate control based on a wavelet transform and we compare the results obtained with these two methods for a compression ratio $T = 6$. As no classification is applied, we simply create an embedded bit-stream and cut it in order to reach the global target bit rate fixed for the CIS. The artifacts

are not visible without any post-processing like an histogram equalization and a zoom on each reconstructed image. If we concentrate our comparison on a particular area of "Genoa" (Fig 4), we can observe that an EZW encoder returns a better quality of reconstruction. Indeed, we keep the sharpness of the edges, especially on the breakwaters of harbor on the right of the image.

Figure 4: Comparison between the two methods for an area of harbor of "Genoa": SPOT5 based on wavelet (a) and EZW progressive transmission without any classification (b). The CIS includes 8 lines

Nevertheless, ringing effects are still visible and only a concrete integration of quality concept will improve the local quality in such areas. So, we set up a local bit rate control based on a classification of wavelet coefficients. First of all, since the memory constraint is less strict, we process the image in CIS of sixty-four lines.

A visual analysis of reconstructed images (Fig 5) shows that our method performs a reduction of ringing artifacts, namely on the boundaries between high activity areas and uniform ones.

An analysis with objective criterions, such as the Fränti one [1] or the local SNR (Signal Noise Ratio)(3), confirms these observations but also allows to see the areas of the rest of the CIS which are damaged. Thus, the values of the mean local SNR computed on two different areas extracted from the same CIS of "Genoa" (Tab 1) prove that we have really privileged the first one (the harbor) with regard to the second (the city).

$$SNR_{local} = \frac{\text{variance}_{signal}}{\text{variance}_{error}} \quad (3)$$

Figure 5: Comparison between the two methods on "Genoa": Progressive transmission with EZW (a) and progressive transmission with modified EZW with classification (b). Both are applied on CIS of 64 lines

SNR_{mean}	Harbor	City
EZW without classification	28	20.8
EZW with classification	51.6	14.6

Table 1: Variation of the mean SNR on two areas of "Genoa" for the two methods, EZW without and with classification

However, the damage concern essentially texture-based regions, such as cities, where artifacts are less awkward for our application. We can convince ourselves by looking at the area of city mentioned in the table (Fig 6): the artifacts are not really important even if the value of SNR is quite low.

6 CONCLUSION

The bit rate control method we present is developed as part of an on-board compression with target ratios greater than 6. The results show the interest of a local regulation loop with a classification of wavelet coefficients. Indeed, it is confirmed that a previous classification in the transform field involves a quality improvement on the critical areas without strongly degrading the rest of the image. However, such an implementation requires an evolution of on-board equipment.

In the future, an evolution of the global bit rate per CIS, by setting up a global regulation loop, would be inserted. Moreover, we shall consider the whole classification, that is the three classes, and develop an extended local regulation method. Thus, an alternative way in order to

Figure 6: Comparison between the two methods for the area of city of "Genoa": Progressive transmission with EZW (a) and progressive transmission with modified EZW with classification (b). Both are applied on CIS of 64 lines

privilege some areas is to compile weighted wavelet coefficients of a CIS within a unique embedded bit-stream.

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